

राष्ट्रहिताय संस्कृतम्

Vol. X, Issue-I, 01, January – June: 2024

ISSN: 2277-7067

Kavikulaguru Kalidas Sanskrit University

Ramtek, Dist. Nagpur, Maharashtra

Peer Reviewed

**Journal of
Fundamental &
Comparative Research**

UGC CARE Listed Journal

शोधसंहिता

New Research Frontiers

Research Journal
ISSN No. 2277-7067

Journal of Fundamental & Comparative Research

शोधसंहिता

A Peer Reviewed Bi-annual Interdisciplinary Research
Journal of the University

UGC CARE Listed Journal
New Research Frontiers

- Patron -

Prof. Shrinivasa Varkhedi
Vice Chancellor

- Chief Editor -

Prof. Madhusudan Penna
Director, Research & Publication

- Editor -

Dr. Rajendra C. Jain
Dept. of Sanskrit Language & Literature

राजकुलसंस्कृतम्

KAVIKULAGURU KALIDAS SANSKRIT UNIVERSITY
RAMTEK

A Bi-annual Interdisciplinary Research Journal of KKSU
Peer Reviewed Journal of Fundamental & Comparative Research

शोधसंहिता

Patron : **Prof. Shrinivasa Varkhedi**
Hon'ble Vice Chancellor

Chief Editor : **Prof. Madhusudan Penna**
Director, Research & Publication, KKSU

Editor : **Dr. Rajendra C. Jain**
Dept. of Sanskrit Language & Literature

Co-Editor : **Dr. Deepak Kapade, Librarian (I/c)**
Dr. Renuka Bokare, PRO, KKSU

Editorial Board :

- Prof. Nanda J. Puri
- Prof. Lalita Chandratre
- Prof. Krishnakumar Pandey
- Prof. Vijaykumar C. G.
- Prof. Kavita Holey

Peer Review Committee :

- Dr. Leena Rastogi, Nagpur
- Dr. V. Subrahmanyam, Hyderabad
- Dr. Dinesh Rasal, Pune
- Dr. Upendra Bhargav, Ujjain
- Dr. Archana Aloni, Nagpur
- Dr. Dinkar Marathe, Ratnagiri

Published by : Registrar, KKSU, Ramtek

© KKSU, Ramtek

कविकुलगुरु कलिदास

**KAVIKULAGURU KALIDAS SANSKRIT UNIVERSITY
RAMTEK**

INDEX

1	CHANGING DIMENSIONS OF RIGHT TO PRIVACY IN INDIA : A JURISPRUDENTIAL ASPECTS	1
2	श्रीलाल शुक्ल के व्यंग्यों में सामाजिक सरोकार	9
3	THE THEME OF RELATIONSHIPS IN R.K NARAYAN'S <i>SWMAY AND FRIENDS</i>	12
4	AN EXPERIMENTAL EFFECT OF BACILLUS CONCRETE SUBTILIS ON CONVENTIONAL CONCRETE	18
5	"VOICES UNHEARD: EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON POLITICAL PARTICIPATION AMONG THE BANJARA COMMUNITY IN CHIKKAMGALURU, KARNATAKA"	24
6	दादा साहब फाल्के : स्वदेशी सिनेमा के पुरोधा	34
7	भारत में विज्ञान के विकास में औपनिवेशिक सरकार की भूमिका (1707 -1857)	39
8	जिला बड़वानी के शहरी एवं ग्रामीण क्षेत्र में निवासित अनुसूचित जनजाति के पुरुषों की सामाजिक स्थिति का तुलनात्मक अध्ययन	43
9	झाबुआ जिले की जनजातियों की वर्तमान सांस्कृतिक परिस्थिति का अध्ययन	48
10	HISTORICAL CONSCIENCE OF BRAJBHASHA POETS	55
11	भारतीय कृषि और किसान ;3000 ई. पू. से 600 ई. पू. तक	61
12	THE TRIAL OF MEERUT CONSPIRACY CASE	64
13	A REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY	71
14	HEALTH CONDITIONS OF ELDERLY PEOPLE IN SPSR NELLORE DISTRICT OF ANDHRA PRADESH	79
15	EPIDTECT: A CUTTING-EDGE WEB-BASED APPLICATION FOR ADVANCED SYMPTOM-BASED DIAGNOSTIC ASSISTANT EXCLUSIVELY FOR MEDICAL PROFESSIONALS	87
16	A STUDY TO ASSESS THE KNOWLEDGE REGARDING VALSALVA MANEUVER AMONG THE B.SC NURSING STUDENTS IN SELECTED NURSING COLLEGE OF KANPUR, UTTAR PRADESH"	91
17	महिलाओं की राजनैतिक सहभागिता का विप्लेषण	102
18	जनजातीय विकास में सरकारी नीतियों की भूमिका एवं चुनौतियां	105
19	"A DESCRIPTIVE STUDY TO ASSESS THE KNOWLEDGE REGARDING THE IMPORTANCE OF INNOVATIVE NATURAL BIRTH TECHNIQUES AMONG B.SC NURSING STUDENTS IN SELECTING NURSING COLLEGE OF KANPUR, UTTAR PRADESH"	109

CHANGING DIMENSIONS OF RIGHT TO PRIVACY IN INDIA: A JURISPRUDENTIAL ASPECT

DR. GAURAV KAUSHIK, Associate Professor, Faculty of Law, Dr. B.R. Ambedkar
University, Agra College, Agra, Uttar Pradesh India

Abstract

Although it is not explicitly mentioned in the Indian Constitution, Article 21, which guarantees the right to life and personal liberty, has significantly shaped the right to privacy. The Supreme Court's interpretations of the law over the years have broadened the meaning of Article 21 to include privacy as an essential component of life and liberty. This article looks at how the right to privacy has changed in India, especially since landmark decisions like Justice K.S. Puttaswamy v. Union of India (2017) and Kharak Singh v. State of Uttar Pradesh (1962) made privacy a fundamental right. The paper also looks at current issues like balancing privacy with state interests, technological advancements like data collection and surveillance, and the growing role of digital platforms. It looks at the tensions between privacy and other rights like freedom of speech, national security, and public safety, as well as the legal and policy frameworks that are needed to protect privacy in a digital age that is changing quickly. Through this analysis, the article aims to present an understanding of how the concept of privacy has been interpreted by Indian courts, the extent of its protection, and the implications of these evolving interpretations for citizens' rights in a democratic society.

Keywords– Right to privacy, Article 21, K.S. Puttaswamy v. Union of India, Digital privacy Supreme Court of India, Data collection and surveillance

I Introduction

The concept of privacy cannot be viewed as static or one-dimensional due to its inherent complexity. It could simply be interpreted as a collection of rights. The actions or activities that we wish to conceal from the general public are one way to define the term "private." In their seminal paper titled "The Right to Privacy," Warren and Brandeis first defined "the concept of privacy rights as a human right". In their writings, numerous philosophers have made mention of the concept of privacy. Aristotle's distinction of an "individual's existence into two domains serves as an excellent illustration of this point. the polis, which is the public sphere, and the oikos, which is the domestic sphere, respectively". J. Bentham acknowledged "the presence of a private aspect in an individual's life". Shakespeare had his "own interpretations of 'private', which he described as 'undeclared' and included an idea of social concealment".

Nonetheless, "a question that the opposition to the right to privacy instantly presents is the definition of 'privacy' and the extent of the application of the right to privacy". An effective method for defining privacy "is to achieve a balance between reductionist and anti-reductionist perspectives. Seven The reductionist perspective posits that the scope of privacy and its infringement should be defined by the government. The legislature would be able to implement privacy in this manner, recognizing it as a fundamental right. However, in the end, it would restrict the scope of privacy and the extent to which judicial review could enhance it".

In “Justice K.S. Puttaswamy (Retd) versus Union of India, a six-decade struggle resulted in the protection of the Right to Privacy, which is now recognized as a fundamental right”. The growth of this right is seen via many rulings that illustrate the courts' differing views at various points in time. Over the years, a nuanced distinction has been established by granting privacy without elevating it to the position of a fundamental right.

In India, the situation has been clarified following the judgment in “K. Puttaswamy v. Union of India, which established that the Right to Privacy is a Fundamental right, albeit not absolute, and therefore subject to unspecified reasonable restrictions. Individuals advocate for the right to privacy as a basic entitlement; nevertheless, the government exhibits little support for this principle”.

II. CONST. AND LEGAL STATUS OF “RIGHT TO PRIVACY” POSITION DURING 1975-2000

In “Gobind v. State of Madhya Pradesh , the Supreme Court determined that a restricted right to privacy is implicit within Part III of the Constitution, stemming from Articles 19(a), 19(d), and 21. It was observed that the aforementioned right is not absolute and is subject to reasonable constraints due to competing public interests. In this ruling, Justice Mathew, considering US jurisprudence, noted that the right to privacy is within the penumbral areas of the Fundamental Rights specifically enshrined in Part III of the Constitution”.

S.C. in “Sunil Batra v. Delhi Admn observed that a minimal infringement of a prisoner’s privacy is unavoidable as the officers have an obligation to keep a watch and ensure that their other human rights are being duly observed. On the contrary, the Court in Malak Singhv. State of P&H held that surveillance is a direct encroachment upon an individual’s right to privacy”. Moreover, “the Supreme Court in R. Rajagopal v. State of Tamil Nadu , again asserted that the right to privacy is an implicit right under Art. 21 and has acquired sufficient constitutional status. The Court noted that the said right includes a ‘right to be let alone’ and the right ‘to safeguard the privacy of his own, his family, marriage, procreation, motherhood, child-bearing and education among other matters’ On a similar note, in State of Maharashtra v. Madhukar Narayan Mardikar, the Supreme Court held that even a —woman of easy virtue is entitled to her privacy and nobody has the authority to invade her privacy at their sweet will”. The S.C. in “People’s Union for Civil Liberties v. Union of India held that telephonic conversations are private in nature and thus, telephone-tapping would be unconstitutional unless conducted by a procedure established by law. The Court concluded by saying that —we have, therefore, no hesitation in holding that the right to privacy is a part of the right to ‘life and personal liberty’ enshrined under article 21 of the Constitution. Once the facts in each case constitute a right to privacy, article 21 is attracted. The said right cannot be curtailed, except according to procedure established by law”.

The S.C. in “S.P. Gupta v. President of India, held that a balance needs to be struck between the right to information and right to privacy. The Court reiterated the point that a right to privacy is not absolute and can be infringed to serve a serious public concern. In Indian Express v. Union of India, it was thus held that — Public interest in freedom of discussion of which freedom of the press is one aspect stems from the requirement that members of a democratic society should be sufficiently informed that they may influence intelligently, the decisions which may affect themselves”.

The right to privacy is not absolute and may be limited via legal measures to prevent crime, maintain order, safeguard health or morality, or protect the rights and freedoms of other's. The S.C. "in Mr. 'X' v. Hospital 'Z', held that moral considerations cannot be kept at bay and public morality can constitute a —compelling State interest warranting a lawful infringement of the right to privacy".

Evolution from 2000 to today

The "Right to Privacy, recognized as a basic right, was secured after a six-decade struggle in the case of Justice K.S. Puttaswamy (Retd) versus Union of India. The growth of this right is seen via many rulings that illustrate the courts' differing views throughout time. Over the years, a nuanced distinction has been established by granting privacy without elevating it to the position of a fundamental right. Initially, the decision of M.P. Sharma v. Satish Chandra in 1954, adjudicated by an eight-judge panel, established that the Constitution's drafters did not intend to subordinate the authority of search and seizure to a fundamental right to privacy. The verdict does not address the legal issue of whether the constitutional right to privacy is safeguarded by any other basic right, such as the right to life and personal liberty".

The subsequent ruling "occurred in 1962 in the case of Kharak Singh v. State of Uttar Pradesh, wherein a six-judge bench determined that the right to privacy is not a fundamental right; nevertheless, it favored the right to privacy by citing police regulations concerning unauthorized night domiciliary visits as an infringement on personal liberty. The limited interpretation of Article 21, which disregarded any shortcomings in the system established by law as determined in the AK Gopalan case, was expanded by the 1978 Maneka Gandhi decision, which asserted that the procedure must be equitable, fair, and reasonable. The multifaceted component encompasses the right to privacy afforded to women of easy virtue, as established in the decision of State of Maharashtra v. Madhukar Narain in 1991".

The significant ruling concerning "privacy rights in India is R. Rajagopal v. State of Tamil Nadu, 1994, in which the Supreme Court determined that the right to privacy is implicit in the right to life and liberty guaranteed to the citizens of this country by Article 21. It constitutes a right to privacy. A citizen have the right to protect the privacy of personal concerns, including family, marriage, reproduction, motherhood, childbearing, and education, among others. The Supreme Court determined that the right to privacy is not an unconditional right and may be restricted to prevent crime, maintain order, safeguard health or morality, or defend the rights and freedoms of others, as established in the case of Mr. X v. Hospital Z in 1995".

In "PUCL v. UOI, popularly known as the Phone Tapping Case', it was held that telephone tapping is a serious invasion of an individual's right to privacy. Moreover, in the case of Selvi v. State of Karnataka, it was held that involuntary subjection of a person to tests such as narco-analysis, polygraph examination and the BEAP also violates the right to privacy. It may be a fundamental right under Article 21 of the Constitution but is not an absolute right and it should not be resorted to by the state unless there is a public emergency or interest of public safety requires. The court didn't define the right to privacy and ruled that it depends on facts and circumstances of every case".

Another "landmark judgment in this regard is the case of Ram Jethmalani v. Union of India that came in the year 2011, in which it was held that —Right to privacy is an integral part of right to life, a cherished constitutional value and it is important that human beings be allowed domains of freedom that are free of public scrutiny unless they act in an unlawful manner. Finally a unanimous judgment was passed by the Supreme Court's nine judge bench in Justice

K.S Puttaswamy v. Union of India overruling the eight judges MP Sharma and six judges Kharak Singh's judgment on right to privacy. This resounding victory guarantees right to privacy as a fundamental right under Article 21 of Part III of the Constitution which is subject to reasonable restrictions. This 547 pages long judgment is the outcome of the petition challenging the constitutional validity of the biometrics system in Aadhar. Although, the court remained silent on infringement of privacy rights in Aadhar card that will be decided later by a smaller bench. Number of petitions have been filed against Aadhar and finally the five-judge bench constituted in the Aadhar case which reserved its judgment. It is challenged on the grounds of violation of right to privacy, unconstitutionality of Aadhar Act, Conditional welfare, Absence of consent and that it is an instrument of mass surveillance".

III. JURISPRUDENTIAL OVERVIEW

In order to comprehend how various academics have interpreted and articulated their views on the "Right to Privacy" throughout time, it is essential to examine the jurisprudential perspective of this right after discussing the Right to Privacy's history. The government contends that the Court is unable to accept a legal concept that is too hazy and uncertain, rendering it unsuitable for constitutional examination. This calls for a look at how privacy came to be and how it has changed over time.

The "Greek philosopher Aristotle spoke of a division between the public sphere of political affairs (which he termed the polis) and the personal sphere of human life (termed Oikos). This dichotomy may provide early recognition of—a confidential zone on behalf of the citizen. Aristotle's distinction between the public and private realms can be regarded as providing a basis for restricting governmental authority to activities falling within the public realm. On the other hand, activities in the private realm are more appropriately reserved for—private reflection, familial relations and self-determination".

The development of privacy doctrine has, to some extent, adhered to the public-private dichotomy. "William Blackstone in his Commentaries on the Laws of England (1765) spoke about this distinction while dividing wrongs into private wrongs and public wrongs. Private wrongs are an infringement merely of particular rights concerning individuals and are in the nature of civil injuries. Public wrongs constitute a breach of general and public rights affecting the whole community and according to him, are called crimes and misdemeanors".

John Stuart Mill in his essay, "On Liberty (1859) gave expression to the need to preserve a zone within which the liberty of the citizen would be free from the authority of the state. According to Mill: —The only part of the conduct of anyone, for which he is amenable to society, is that which concerns others. In the part which merely concerns himself, his independence is, of right, absolute. Over himself, over his own body and mind, the individual is sovereign. While speaking of a—struggle between liberty and authority, Mill posited that the tyranny of the majority could be reined by the recognition of civil rights such as the individual right to privacy, free speech, assembly and expression".

Austin "in his Lectures on Jurisprudence (1869) spoke of the distinction between the public and the private realms: jus publicum and jus privatum. The distinction between the public and private realms has its limitations. If the reason for protecting privacy is the dignity of the individual, the rationale for its existence does not cease merely because the individual has to interact with others in the public arena. The extent to which an individual expects privacy in a public street may be different from that which she expects in the sanctity of the home".

Madison, J., “who was the architect of the American Constitution, contemplated the protection of the faculties of the citizen as an incident of the inalienable property rights of human beings. In his words: —In the former sense, a man’s land, or merchandise, or money is called his property. In a word, as a man is said to have a right to his property, he may be equally said to have a property in his rights. To guard a man’s house as his castle, to pay public and enforce private debts with the most exact faith, can give no title to invade a man’s conscience which is more sacred than his castle, or to withhold from it that debt of protection, for which the public faith is pledged, by the very nature and original conditions of the social pact”.

In an essay published on December 15, 1890, “in the Harvard Law Review, Samuel D. Warren and Louis Brandeis referenced the development of the law to include the right to life as a recognition of man's spiritual nature, his feelings, and his intellect. As legal rights expanded, the right to life evolved to signify the right to enjoy life – the right to privacy. Warren and Brandeis elucidate the notion that the experiences of pain, pleasure, and profit extend beyond the physical realm, necessitating legal acknowledgment of thoughts, emotions, and sensations. They insightfully highlight the influence of technology on the right to privacy, asserting that recent innovations and business practices underscore the imperative for enhanced protections of the individual, as articulated by Judge Cooley's concept of the right to be let alone”.

In “seminal article, Warren and Brandeis observed that:- The principle which protects personal writings and all other personal productions, not against theft and physical appropriation, but against publication in any form, is in reality not the principle of private property, but that of an inviolate personality. Though many contemporary accounts attribute the modern conception of the right to privacy’ to the Warren and Brandeis article, historical material indicates that it was Thomas Cooley who adopted the phrase —the right to be let alone , in his Treatise on the Law of Torts. Discussing personal immunity, Cooley stated:- the right of one’s person may be said to be a right of complete immunity; the right to be alone”.

Roscoe Pound described “the Warren and Brandeis’s article as have done —nothing less than adding a chapter to our law . However, another writer on the subject states that:- This right to privacy was not new. Warren and Brandeis did not even coin the phrase, —right to privacy, nor its common soubriquet, —the right to be let alone. The right to be let alone is a part of the right to enjoy life. The right to enjoy life is, in its turn, a part of the fundamental right to life of the individual. The right to privacy was developed by Warren and Brandeis in the backdrop of the dense urbanization which occurred particularly in the East Coast of the United States. Between 1790 and 1890, the US population had risen from four million to sixty-three million. The population of urban areas had grown over a hundred-fold since the end of the civil war. In 1890, over eight million people had immigrated to the US”.

Technological advancements and swift advances have subjected the private sphere to strain. The “newspaperization” trend, characterized by the growing prominence of print media in American culture, came along with this. “E.L. Godkin, a journalist, published a piece on the same subject in Scribner's magazine in July 1890, six months prior to the publication of the Warren and Brandeis essay. Godkin, on the other hand, had no other option but to use coercive tools like the cudgel or the horsewhip to protect privacy. Warren and Brandeis stood for upholding the right to privacy through common law”.

The concept “that people possess rights against the State that precede rights established by explicit legislation has been articulated within a liberal legal theory proposed by Ronald Dworkin. In his seminal work titled —Taking Rights Seriously Working asserts the existence

of a right against the government as essential to protecting the dignity of the individual. Hence it can be said that all the scholar have a very dynamic view and vary from each other regarding the privacy provision of an individual and whether they should be provided to the individuals or not and whether they can enforce that right against the state”.

THE MULTIDIMENSIONAL ASPECT

The Right to Privacy verdict has a multifaceted influence on the lives of 1.34 billion Indians, including aspects such as sexual orientation and the exchange of information, including Aadhaar.

Biometric data like “fingerprints and iris scans are among the most private types of information to disclose. The biometric and demographic information of approximately 1.17 billion Indians in the Aadhar system can be used for government surveillance. By creating a comprehensive profile of a person's spending habits, social connections, property ownership, and a wealth of other information, it makes profiling easier”.

As pointed out by “Justice D Y Chandrachud that we are in an era of ubiquitous dataveillance’ where data mining; infringement of informational privacy by information control; Know Your Customer (KYC) which provides intimate information to the organization; National Intelligence Grid (NATGRID) that seeks to integrate over 25 categories of database from agencies and make it available to law enforcement officers are a facet of right to privacy. Google, Facebook, Amazon have much more information of their customers than the government which leads to profiling. Companies track the personal preferences of online shopping and target individuals for the purpose of advertisement. Also, the judgment may force the mobile companies to change the data privacy and protection settings”.

The S.C. said “that the unlawful disclosure of an individual's medical information constitutes an invasion of privacy; nevertheless, such documents may be properly used by the state for public health preservation and policy formulation. Euthanasia, when considered with the right to privacy, grants the authority to end one's life. Justice J Chelameswar said, “An individual's right to decline life-prolonging medical treatment or to end their life constitutes an additional freedom encompassed within the right to privacy.” Earlier Supreme Court held that the right to life does not include right to die and recommended the Parliament to consider the feasibility of deleting section 309 of IPC”.

Balakrishnan K.G. wrote — “There is no doubt that a woman's right to make reproductive choices is also a dimension of —personal liberty as understood under Article 21... which also includes right to —abstain from procreating. Family, marriage, procreation and sexual orientation are all integral to the dignity of the individual. The court said that sexual orientation is an essential attribute of right to privacy which affects the previous judgment criminalizing homosexuality”.

CONCLUDING REMARKS:

When studying the history of privacy as a right in India, one can observe the shifting interpretations of the Supreme Court's jurisprudence. In its preliminary rulings, the Court did not recognize the Right to Privacy as a fundamental right. Over time, the Supreme Court's views on the cases it heard changed. The right to privacy was recently elevated to the status of a fundamental right in Article 21, Part III of the Constitution. The evolving concept may be attributed to recent technological advancements that have resulted in the extensive processing

of personal data. Social networking sites, commercial online retailers, and a number of shady organizations have all collected personal information from individuals, including credit card numbers and date of birth. Multinational corporations have taken advantage of legal loopholes to obtain consent for the accumulation of user data by presenting an end-user license or agreement of thousands of words. The average person neither fully comprehends nor has the time to read these intricate legal agreements. The egregious exploitation of legal deficiencies has precipitated a movement that today asserts privacy as a fundamental right. Privacy encompasses other elements beyond the extracted numerical data. It encompasses an individual's thoughts, which may range from sexual orientation to political opinions, and he desires to maintain their confidentiality. The state may argue that keeping track of people's actions is necessary for national security. However, there exists no definition, rule, or mandate delineating the boundaries of the state's obligation to safeguard the nation's interests. However, the circumstances vary globally, and the extensive OECD rules delineate the constraints that must be imposed on the handling of personal data. There are three basic tenets that can be applied to this authority: proportionality, legitimacy, and transparency. The repercussions of privacy are crucial to the various interests of individuals; Consequently, this right must be upheld and protected.

References

- Aristotle, Jowett, B., & Davis, H. W. C. (1908). *Aristotle's politics*. Clarendon Press.
- Aruna Ramchandra Shanbaug v. Union of India & Ors., Writ Petition (Criminal) No. 115 of 2009, Decided on 7 March, 2011.
- Bhuyan, A. (2018, January 18). Aadhaar isn't just about privacy: There are 30 challenges the govt is facing in Supreme Court. *The Wire*. <https://thewire.in/government/aadhaar-privacy-government-supreme-court>
- Bowers v. Hardwick, 478 U.S. 186 (1986).
- Cannataci, J. A. (2015). *The individual and privacy*. Routledge.
- Chaturvedi, A. (2018, May 10). Aadhaar hearing concludes in Supreme Court: Here's what was argued over 38 days. *Bloomberg Quint*. <https://www.bloomberquint.com/aadhaar/2018/05/10/aadhaar-hearing-concludes-in-supreme-court-heres-what-was-argued-over-38-days>
- Cooley, T. (1888). *Treatise on the law of torts* (2nd ed.).
- Dhananjay, M., & Choudhary, A. A. (2017, August 24). Right to privacy is a fundamental right, it is intrinsic to right to life: Supreme Court. *The Times of India*. <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/india/right-to-privacy-is-a-fundamental-right-supreme-court/articleshow/60203394.cms>
- Dworkin, R. (1977). *Taking rights seriously*. Duckworth.
- Glancy, D. J. (1979). The invention of the right to privacy. *Arizona Law Review*, 21(1), 1.
- Gobind v. State of Madhya Pradesh, AIR 1975 SC 1378.
- Gobind v. State of Madhya Pradesh, (1975) 2 SCC 148; Griswold v. Connecticut, 381 U.S. 479; Roe v. Wade, 410 U.S. 113.
- Gian Kaur v. State of Punjab, 1996(2) SCC 648.
- Indian Constitution, Art. 21.
- Indian Drugs and Pharmaceuticals Ltd. v. Workmen, (2007) 1 SCC 408.
- Indian Express v. Union of India, AIR 1982 SC 149.
- Jain, M. P. (2014). *Indian constitutional law* (7th ed., p. 166).
Journal of Kavikulaguru Kalidas Sanskrit University, Ramtek

- James, M. C. (2014). A comparative analysis of the right to privacy in the United States, Canada, and Europe. *Connecticut Journal of International Law*, 29(2), 261.
- Kaushik, K., & Tiwari, R. (2017, August 28). A to Z of privacy. *The Indian Express*.
<http://indianexpress.com/article/explained/fundamental-right-to-privacy-aadhaar-kyc-4816584/>
- Kharak Singh v. State of U.P., 1963 AIR 1295, (1964) 1 SCR 332.
- K. Puttuswamy v. Union of India, (2017) 105 SCC 1.
- K.S. Puttaswamy (Retd) v. Union of India, WRIT PETITION (CIVIL) NO 494 OF 2012.
- Madison, J. (1906). Essay on property. In G. Hunt (Ed.), *The writings of James Madison* (Vol. 6, pp. 101-103).
- Malak Singh v. State of Punjab & Haryana, AIR 1991 SC 760.
- Maneka Gandhi v. Union of India, (1978) 1 SCC 248, AIR 1978 SC 597, 620.
- Math, S. B., & Chaturvedi, S. K. (2012). Euthanasia: Right to life vs right to die. *Indian Journal of Medical Research*, 136(6).
- Mill, J. S. (1859). *On liberty*. Batoche Books.
- Mills, J. L. (2008). *The lost right* (p. 4). Oxford University Press.
- M.P. Sharma v. Satish Chandra, 1954 AIR 300, 1954 SCR 1077.
- Mr. X v. Hospital Z, AIR (1998) 8 SCC 296.
- Negley, G. (1966). Philosophical views on the value of privacy. *Law & Contemporary Problems*, 31, 321-322.
- Pandey, J. N. (2015). *Constitutional law of India* (52nd ed., p. 259).
- Panday, J. (2017, August 28). India's Supreme Court upholds right to privacy as a fundamental right—and it's about time. *Electronic Frontier Foundation*. <https://www.eff.org/deeplinks/2017/08/indias-supreme-court-upholds-right-privacy-fundamental-right-and-its-about-time>
- People's Union for Civil Liberties v. Union of India, AIR 1991 SC 207.
- R. Rajagopal v. State of Tamil Nadu, AIR 1995 SC 264.
- S.P. Gupta v. President of India, AIR 1997 SC 568.
- Selvi v. State of Karnataka, (2010) 7 SCC 263, 370, AIR 2010 SC 1974.
- Shukla, V. N., & Singh, M. P. (2016). *Constitution of India* (12th ed., p. 212).
- State of Maharashtra v. Madhukar Narayan Mardikar, (1978) 4 SCC 494.
- Uppaluri, U., & Shivanagowda, V. (2012). Preserving constitutive values in the modern Panopticon: The case for legislating toward a privacy right in India. *NUJS Law Review*, 5, 21.
- Vaidyanathan, A., & Varma, S. (2017, August 24). Privacy a fundamental right: 10 points on huge Supreme Court verdict. *NDTV*. <https://www.ndtv.com/india-news/right-to-privacy-privacy-is-a-fundamental-right-says-supreme-court-10-developments-1741368>
- Warren, S. D., & Brandeis, L. D. (1890). The right to privacy. *Harvard Law Review*, 4(5), 193-205.
- Writ petition (Civil) no 494 of 2012.